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Addressing gender as part of a Multifactorial Model of professional identity formation in a PoPBL engineering learning environment

A. BADETS
LINEACT, CESI
Rouen, France

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ABSTRACT

Previous studies on the interaction of gender and professional identity formation (PIF) in engineering curricula showed how PBL and group-work could affect female students' experience. An ongoing study on an engineering school's project-oriented, problem-based learning curriculum analyses the interactions of the learning environment and students' personal characteristics with their PIF. This article describes an attempt to draft a multifactorial model of PIF, analysing the relative influences of gender and other factors in the process.

Correlation tests and Multiple Correspondence Analyses were used to sort data collected from questionnaires to a cohort in the programme. Qualitative data from interviews with 31 of these students were also analysed using lexicometric tools.

Data presented in this paper suggest that:

- Environmental factors are more relevant than personal characteristics (including gender) to explain most PIF differences amongst students;
- Gender does affect PIF in two ways in this programme:
 - Female students resort more to external resources (p-value=0.020) and tutoring (p-value=0.05);
 - Female students express more career goals flexibility (p-value=0.017).

Three perspectives arise to use this draft of a multifactorial model of PIF to develop curriculum inclusiveness:

1. Address gender as part of a global scheme to address diversity via tools valuing individuals' qualities [7];
2. Address diversity management through tutoring, which is the most relevant factor for several indicators of PIF;
3. Use experience expression as a reflexive tool for students and teachers, and for research design purposes.

1 STUDY CONTEXT: ADDRESSING PROFESSIONAL IDENTITY FORMATION AND DIVERSITY IN A POPBL ENGINEERING CURRICULUM

1.1 CESI's PoPBL engineering curriculum specificities

CESI, a French multicentre school of engineering, has implemented a project-oriented, problem-based learning (PoPBL) curriculum in its work-and-study engineering programme since 2015. In this curriculum, based on group work in teams of six, new teams are created for each of the 12 projects the students conduct, and a member of the teaching staff tutors up to 6 teams at a time.

This study focuses on the cohort that undertook the 3-year engineering degree programme, from October 2015 to September 2018. In this curriculum, the students specialize through their in-company work (they spend 101 weeks in companies), and during the last year of the school curriculum, when they choose a major. This means students with very different backgrounds (two-year post-secondary degrees in fields as varied as chemistry, quality management, electricity, public works etc.) share the same training on the first 2 years of the curriculum.

The PoPBL dimension of the curriculum, with its team-based collaborative learning, forces these students to cooperate to produce deliverables and solve problems in multidisciplinary projects. Addressing diversity in this curriculum, where students have heterogeneous academic origins but have to work together, seemed an interesting starting point to try and analyse these students' professional identity formation.

1.2 Student diversity in education research and in the curriculum studied

Diversity is a field of interest in education studies, and it is often defined as a cultural, ethnic, socioeconomic, gender and/or ability heterogeneity amongst students that needs to be addressed, and that is related to questions of underrepresentation, inclusion and non-marginalization of all student profiles [1].

A first set of data shows that, in this engineering programme, there is indeed heterogeneity-related issues in the students' profiles, and not only academically speaking. As far as gender diversity is concerned, female students represent only 12.5% of the student cohort. In group works, a female student will be, most of the time, the only female student in her team. Furthermore, when enquiring their previous work experiences, or expectations, the results confirmed the cohort's heterogeneity¹. For example, 30% of the students had started a career as technicians before going back to training, with the other 70% in their initial training; 60% of the students had a precise idea of their future jobs, when 40% were clueless about their career goals.

This heterogeneity is the reason we wished to address the relative influences of different personal characteristics in the process of these students' professional identity development. The students' characteristics whose impacts on PIF we questioned were both sociodemographic (age and gender²), and dispositional. Student dispositions are

¹ Data collected via a questionnaire to the full cohort of 587 students during their integration week.

² In France, no data on cultural/ethnic/religious diversity can be collected by individual researchers without legal authorization (granted mostly to commissioned survey groups), which explains the

a combination of intrapersonal factors like resources (knowledge and skills), motivation, and persistence, and might impact their behaviour and engagement in a curriculum [2], and play a role in their professionalization process.

When enquiring how this heterogeneity was addressed in this curriculum, we noticed that academic background heterogeneity was indeed addressed, with tutors creating homogeneous teams of students, “handpicking” them according to previous skills and backgrounds. Gender diversity and dispositional diversity (related to motivation, goals etc.) were, however, not addressed.

1.3 Gender in engineering education and professional identity formation

Why focus this paper on the impact of gender, as compared to other factors, on PIF? Women, in 2015, only represented 28,4% of all engineering students in France³. As Beddoes stated, “despite a nearly 40-year history of (...) interventions (...), women remain significantly underrepresented in engineering” [3]. Scientific literature in the field points the gender bias that affects female students in engineering education. More specifically, it was pointed out that group work in PBL environments significantly affected female students’ experience [4] [5] and professional identity development [6] and that female and male engineering students identified with different sides of the engineering set of activities.

The concept of professional identity formation is a very interesting framework when studying students’ engineering identities. In this paper, we define PIF as a social “becoming”, supported by the development of a sense of belonging, and the recognition, by learners, peers and supervisors, of the learners’ abilities and legitimacy [7]. PIF is thus always multidimensional. Investigating its relations to gender implies studying the interrelations of gender and other personal factors, as well as environmental influences, in students’ identification, self-recognition, achievements and goals. Fowler [4] mentions the expectancy-value framework as key to questioning the impacts of diversity on student perception of the curriculum, their engagement and how engineering identity might develop differently amongst students. Hence the need to try and build a multifactorial model of PIF, that should allow us to precisely evaluate the relative influences of gender and other factors in the process of PIF.

2 SCOPE OF THE WORK AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

2.1 Research goals and scope

With this study, we wish to:

- Evaluate the impact of this curriculum on male and female students’ professional development, to try and analyse the relations between their gender and their PIF,
- Investigate the interactions of gender diversity and student diversity as a whole in their professional development, to develop a model for understanding PIF,

limitation of sociodemographic data collected here, and the focus on dispositions rather than other personal characteristics.

³ Source : *Sous-direction des systèmes d'information et des études statistiques -SIES*

- Address PBL curricula's inclusiveness, and the way to support the thriving of students of varied profiles in such curricula.

The PoPBL environment implemented at CESI is not a targeted program, which means it is not an institutionalized attempt to build an inclusive engineering environment [7]. It is a new curriculum implemented in a 35 year-old programme, with new teaching, learning and evaluating methods. The impacts it can have “diversity-wise”, and the question of this programme being “diversity-inclusive” is an issue for inquiry by the author, but not for the curriculum designers⁴.

The personal factors investigated that we hypothesized might impact students' PIF, and that we will cover in this paper are: their biological gender, age, previous experiences, goals and expectations. The environmental factors inquired were the students' training centre (the same training takes place simultaneously in 9 different locations across the country, with cohorts of different sizes), and project tutors.

The indicators of professional identity development addressed here are:

- Students' identification to an engineering posture (they were asked what an engineer was to them, and if they felt they were able to act like engineers during school projects),
- Students' self-efficacy in an engineering posture (they were asked about their confidence in their success in different tasks, full projects, and different roles in groups)
- Conscience of their development and feeling of recognition/legitimacy (they were asked what skills they thought they acquired, during various tasks and projects, and if they felt these skills were acknowledged by peers/tutors),
- Challenges and support experienced in the process and overall satisfaction.

Previous scientific literature on the field allowed us to define these intrinsic indicators of PIF (as opposed to external indicators like the acquisition of key engineering skills) as our main focus.

⁴ The author, during the 3 years of data collection, was a project manager responsible for diversity-related awareness campaigns directed to secondary school students, as well as a researcher in education at the same institution.

2.2 Methodology and data collected

Five questionnaires were submitted to the cohort throughout the 3-year survey, with the following answer rates (*Table 1*):

Table 1. Data collected via questionnaires to the cohort of 587 throughout the 3 years

Questionnaire	1 Year 1 – October 2015	2 Year 1 – May 2016	3 Year 2 – November 2016	4 Year 2 – May 2017	5 Year 3 - November 2017
Number of full answers	587	102	232	228	155

Statistical analyses (flat sorting, Chi-square correlation tests and Multiple Correspondence Analyses) were used to sort the data collected from these surveys and allowed us to have access to global data and statistical analyses on the full cohort’s experience of the curriculum.

To get more in-depths insight and nuance into the correlations noted in the cohort results, a sample of 31 of the students, from 6 different training centres delivering the same programme, took part to 68 interviews over the 3 years as well. These qualitative data were first categorized by the author, using literature-driven PIF indicators, as well as field-induced ones. To analyse the frequency and strength of each category according to various personal and environmental characteristics, the lexicometric tool Sonal was used.

3 RESULTS

Although gender can be pinpointed as a relevant factor in students’ career goals adjustment and use of resources, other personal characteristics that cannot be related solely to gender (students’ expectations of the programme), as well as environmental factors, seem to play a bigger role in students’ PIF than gender only.

3.1 Diversity as a difficulty

The first significant piece of data we would like to report here is the crucial importance students give to “others” in their development in this curriculum, whether it be as a tool to become themselves, or as obstacles on their way. Amongst the sample of students, 71% mention teamwork as a help during their first interview. Mutual aid and cooperation as tools to gain knowledge and leadership skills are the most mentioned resources to their development. But group work is also mentioned as the main difficulty encountered by the whole sample of students. What they find difficult with group work is the varied implication of the different team members in the projects, and the “non-professional” quality of their relations to each other, that is especially regretted by students identifying themselves with a manager-type engineer. Tensions arise from group work and from the diversity of students’ engagement in the curriculum.

3.2 Factors that affect professional identity formation in this curriculum

When looking at all the factors that impact students' PIF, the cohort data collected suggest that environmental factors (*Table 2*) are most of the time more relevant than personal characteristics (including gender) to explain most PIF differences amongst students.

What the below-mentioned data (*Table 2*) imply is that being in one or another training centre, or being tutored by one or another tutor does have significant impact on:

- How the students will or will not identify to engineering identities,
- How they will or will not feel recognized as engineers by their peers and tutors,
- The challenges they will or will not perceived in STEM topics.

These PIF indicators are not related to any of the personal factors enquired. However, personal factors do have an impact on students' PIF as *Table 2* shows.

Table 2. Significant correlations (Chi square p-value) between environmental, personal factors and students' professional identity development indicators⁵(tool: XLSTAT)

Related factors		PIF indicators							
		Identification to an engineering identity	Self-efficacy	Recognition as an engineer	Challenges in STEM topics	Support in group work	Career goals evolution	Support in tutoring	Satisfaction of expectations
External	Project tutor	0.050	0.045	0.012	NS	NS	NS	0.018	NS
	Training centre	0.033	0.045	0.007	0.001	0.023	0.048	0.018	NS
Personal factors	Previous academic background	NS	NS	NS	NS	0.024	NS	NS	0.049
	age	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	0.044
	gender	NS	0.003	NS	NS	NS	0.017	0.005	NS
	expectations	NS	NS	NS	NS	0.047	NS	NS	0,029

Personal factors are the sole factors of influence on the overall student satisfaction of the curriculum, which is related to their previous academic background, expectations and age-range. Personal factors co-influence (with environmental factors) other PIF indicators: self-efficacy, the support encountered, as well as career goals evolution.

Multiple Correspondence Analyses (on cohort data) reveal that environmental factors can reinforce or diminish the effect of initial predispositions caused by personal factors. For example, both gender and tutoring can be significantly related to students' self-confidence. When comparing the relative influences of these factors (gender versus tutoring) on self-efficacy, via MCA, tutoring appears to be the most influential factor. So if we can relate to Fowler's finding [4] of female students' "lower sense of self

⁵ NS is for « not significant », i.e. a p-value>0.05

efficacy” in STEM, tutoring affects this indicator even more strongly. Tutors can diminish (and increase) this gender bias. The same phenomenon occurs with teamwork as a support to students’ PIF: though impacted by personal factors, such as students’ previous experiences, this indicator is more impacted by environmental elements.

Gender does affect PIF in two major ways in this programme: it clearly affects students’ career goals flexibility and their use of resources in the curriculum. When compared (MCA on cohort data) to environmental influences on students’ career goals, gender is the most significant factor, and when compared to the impact of the training centres on the use of the tutor as a resource, gender is, again, the most significant factor. These are the only two significant gender differences that are not counterbalanced by tutorial posture or other environmental elements. The impact of this bias is confirmed by the sample’s data: 3 out of the 31 people in the sample considered completely changing their career path and quitting engineering. The 3 were women. This piece of data, though not statistically significant, raises the issue of female students’ persistence and well-being. Although data collected from the cohort does not underline such gender biased team dynamics as found in previous studies (Fowler’s for example), gender does have an impact on students’ experience in the curriculum, and their “becoming” engineers.

The other personal characteristics that are most significantly related to PIF indicators appear to be students of both genders’ expectations and previous experiences. These personal characteristics are indeed the most relevant factors of impact on students’ support experienced in the curriculum, and their overall satisfaction.

3.3 Impact of methodological design on data collection

We mentioned that, in the cohort-related data, environment is more relevant than personal factors to the expression of teamwork difficulties. We are however able to point out a major difference between data collected from the cohort and data collected from the sample (i.e. qualitative data). Indeed, the sample data appears to bring more nuanced, and more gender-related differences between students’ PIF.

For example, in the sample of students interviewed, female students tend to express significantly more how they use teamwork as a rehearsal for their future role as managers and group coordinator. They also tend to mention more the difficulty to lead and more basically to put to work the teams of their peers, pinpointing the lack of “maturity” of their (male) peers and even, for two of the female students in the sample, expressing a feeling of being marginalized because of their engagement in the curriculum. All the while, male students tend to express how they use teamwork as a way to co-develop their knowledge, and as a source of social networking.

Gender differences, as well as other more implicit and subtle differences related to personal characteristics, arise in the qualitative data collection, which encourages us to question the impact of research design on the analysis of “sensitive” data related to identity and diversity. The biases related to the different “quality” of the data collected

can be numerous. First of all, the author of this paper and research project is female, and takes part to affirmative actions aimed at building awareness on gender bias in engineering studies. Although this activity was never mentioned during the interviews, and the same questions were asked to male and female students, this bias is still likely. Moreover, more female students took part to the interview process than the cohort's female/male ratio accounts for. This can lead us to confirm that female and male students do not behave and engage in the same way in student/staff relationships in the curriculum, but it also forces us to carefully nuance the scope of the results related to the sample's data, as they are less representative than the cohort's data.

Just like most curricula may not yet be designed to embrace student diversity, we agree with Beddoes et al. [5] that “the dominant research designs and approaches may not be the best for capturing the experiences of minority groups or understanding gender in teamwork”. Altogether, it appears that collecting qualitative data can be a very precious source of nuanced and more implicit information when dealing with such issues as professional identity formation and diversity, especially when trying to develop a viable model of the process.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

4.1 The model of PIF in this curriculum

What the data collected show is that, although there are some “common” developments in all the students' professional identity formation⁶, most of the PIF indicators that we analysed are either influenced by personal factors, including gender, or environmental factors. These diverse transitional paths can lead to a feeling of inadequacy of the curriculum (and, for one third of the cohort, an overall dissatisfaction) to some of the students, when their evaluation of the curriculum does not match their expectancies. The following figure (Figure 1) is an attempt to depict a model of professional identity development in this curriculum, which takes into account the relative influences of personal and environmental factors on PIF indicators, as well as the weight of explicit and more implicit factors of influence.

⁶ We did not focus here on the “common” tools of developments, but the two following factors are mentioned by the cohort as “universal” tools to build one's engineering identity: oral evaluations and problem solving experimentation.

Figure 1 : A model of PIF in this curriculum - personal, environmental, explicit and implicit factors of influence

4.2 Perspectives to make (gender) diversity a support of PIF

The consequence of this heterogeneity in developmental paths, is that the curriculum designers, should they aim at tackling disengagement issues or tensions amongst students, should address gender diversity and dispositional diversity the way background diversity is addressed: by taking action. Indeed, tutoring teams are able to transform background diversity into a strength for each team, building up individuals' confidence thanks to previous experience. This implies tutors selecting team members "so that individual student characteristics and diversity can be considered" ⁷. To transform student diversity into a support of PIF, diversity in all its dimensions (students' goals, expectations, motivation, learning styles, as well as their preferences

⁷ Source: SEFI Position Paper on Diversity, Equality and Inclusiveness in Engineering Education <https://www.sefi.be/publication/sefi-position-paper-on-diversity-equality-and-inclusiveness-in-engineering-education/>

in terms of resources and tutoring) should be addressed and expressed, and not overlooked. An inclusive learning environment cannot be developed if diversity is not acknowledged and if biases are not made explicit, which seems the case for gender diversity in this curriculum. Engineers are often team leaders, and their communication and interpersonal skills are as important as their technical skills. Engineering Education should then use what we've so far learned about professional identity development and the impacts of diversity on it, to develop curriculum inclusiveness. The following strategies could be explored to do so:

1. Exploring activities to address diversity so as to change students' relationship to "otherness" and their expectations towards one another⁸. We would add using experience expression as well, as a reflexive tool for both students and teachers so as to make their skill sets, learning goals and (un)comfort zones more explicit and obvious and to encourage students to reflect on theirs and others' [4], and to allow tutors to adapt their tutoring to such feedback received.
2. A global scheme to address student diversity via tools valuing individuals' qualities [7], so as to avoid treating only part of the problem (dealing with gender diversity, but not addressing differences in expectations, and vice-versa). Addressing diversity in engineering training in all its dimensions to try and model the various characteristics that affect PIF is only a starting point to develop/design engineering curricula that allow students, in their diversity, to thrive and develop their confidence. What kind of tools can be used?
 - French researcher Roux [8] mentions the positive impact of "ritualized social practices" that allow "reciprocal control of the partners during the course of the tasks" in order to deal with student heterogeneity in group work.
 - As far as engineering projects are concerned in a PBL context, researchers at Louvain Learning Lab [9] suggest using « position » cards instead of fixed roles in teamwork so as to be more representative of actual engineering activities in real life projects, but also to allow more flexibility and ensure that interactions between students are structured and symmetrical.
3. Tutoring is key in addressing diversity management in such group work and PBL engineering education contexts. If students' freedom of choice in terms of building a team can be a very formative option in terms of team management, it also appears that task assignment and team composition by tutors can be a good way for students to develop critical interpersonal and communication skills, and for tutors to "disrupt the self-perpetuating feedback loop in which students gain skills and experience according to their pre-existing expertise" [4]... Which also means disrupting stereotypes, habits and biases as much as possible.

4.3 Conclusion

PBL is often presented as a learning environment that is most adapted to a wide variety of student profiles. But we can agree with Du et al. [10], that PBL itself is "not enough to be used as a recipe" for homogeneous student development in a curriculum.

⁸ Atadero et al. 2018 [5] suggest using Student Trading Cards or Sketch-based interaction.

To accommodate the different expectations, academic backgrounds, learning styles, and to tackle disposition-related, as well as gender-related biases in the cohort, the PBL curriculum should be envisioned as a crucible where diversity is addressed and promoted; as an environment “where every individual is not only respected, but also feels safe and included”⁹. This might be achieved through tutoring as a mediation to the social interactions at stake. Some tutors in the curriculum studied have expressed their difficulty with the new professional identity they too have to develop, as tutoring and teaching are different activities that require different skills: they too need to adapt to the new curriculum. Addressing gender and more globally diversity and professional identity formation as a multifactorial model in a PBL environment is then also connected to addressing tutoring identity in a PBL learning environment. Student diversity might stop being a hindrance to students’ well-being and their harmonious development if tutoring identity, and diversity management by tutors were to be systematically addressed at the institutional level of PBL curricula.

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⁹ Source: SEFI Position Paper on Diversity, Equality and Inclusiveness in Engineering Education <https://www.sefi.be/publication/sefi-position-paper-on-diversity-equality-and-inclusiveness-in-engineering-education/>

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